

CONSISTENCY IS THE MAIN REQUIREMENT OF THE PSYCHOLOGY OF TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada tizimlilik-xorijiy tilni o'qitish psixologiyasining asosiy talabi ekanligi haqida so'z boradi. Shuningdek, maqolada psixologiyaning ta'limdagi o'rni va uning pedagogika va tilshunoslik bilan aloqasi o'rganiladi. Maqolada xorijiy tillarni o'qitishda psixologik nazariyalarni qo'llash usullari, o'qituvchining kasbiy til kompetensiyasi, o'quv predmeti va o'quvchilarning individual xususiyatlarini hisobga olish omillari, ayniqsa chet tillarini o'rganish motivatsiyasi muhimligini ta'kidlanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Tizimlilik, xorijiy tilni o'qitish psixologiyasi, metod, pedagogik-psixologiya, tilshunoslik.

Аннотация: В данной статье говорится о том, что системность является основным требованием психологии преподавания иностранного языка. Также в статье рассматривается роль психологии в образовании и ее связь с педагогикой и лингвистикой. В статье подчеркивается важность методов применения психологических теорий при обучении иностранным языкам, профессиональной языковой компетентности преподавателя, факторов, учитывающих предметные и индивидуальные особенности учащихся, особенности мотивации к изучению иностранных языков.

Ключевые слова: Систематика, психология обучения иностранному языку, методика, педагогико-психология, лингвистика.

Abstract: This article states that consistency is the main requirement of the psychology of teaching a foreign language. The article also discusses the role of psychology in education and its connection with pedagogy and linguistics. The article emphasizes the importance of methods for applying psychological theories in teaching foreign languages, the professional language competence of the teacher, factors that take into account the subject and individual characteristics of students, and the characteristics of motivation for learning foreign languages.

Keywords: Systematics, psychology of teaching a foreign language, methodology, pedagogical psychology, linguistics.

When embarking on the journey of learning a new language, consistency emerges as a fundamental pillar for achieving fluency and proficiency. The process of language learning is intricate, involving the acquisition of skills such as reading, writing, listening, and speaking. Consistency in language learning does not merely mean regular practice, but also the persistent application of learned skills in a variety of contexts to deepen understanding and retention.

Continuous Exposure: Regular exposure to the new language is crucial. This can be through reading books, listening to music, watching movies in the target language, or conversing with native speakers. Each interaction with the language reinforces previous knowledge and introduces new vocabulary and structures.

Systematic Practice: Consistent practice helps in solidifying the grammar rules and vocabulary in one's memory. This practice should be systematic and cover all aspects of the language rather than focusing on only one area.

Feedback and Correction: Regular feedback is essential in the learning process. Consistent learning enables learners to receive continuous feedback, understand their mistakes, and work on them promptly.

There are some Strategies to maintain Consistency in Language Learning

Maintaining consistency might be challenging, especially with the distractions and responsibilities of daily life. However, several strategies can help learners stay on track.

Setting Clear Goals: Clear, achievable goals can serve as motivation and provide a roadmap for learners. These goals should be specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound (SMART).

Creating a Study Schedule: A well-structured study schedule is essential. It should allocate specific times for language practice, and these should be adhered to as much as possible.

Using Language Learning Apps: Many language learning apps are designed to encourage daily practice. These can be particularly useful for maintaining consistency, as they often come with reminders and trackers to monitor progress.

Joining Language Groups: Being part of a language learning community can motivate learners to engage regularly. Group activities and discussions can make the learning process more engaging and consistent.

The Impact of Inconsistency on Language Learning

Inconsistency can severely hinder the language learning process, leading to several setbacks.

Forgetting Learned Material: Language learning requires building upon previously acquired knowledge. Inconsistency can lead to forgetting crucial vocabulary and grammar, making progress slow and fragmented.

Lack of Language Immersion: Inconsistent learning fails to simulate the immersive experience necessary for deep language learning. Without regular exposure, the learner's ability to think and express thoughts in the new language remains underdeveloped.

Decreased Motivation: Sporadic learning often leads to a lack of visible progress, which can decrease motivation. This demotivation can create a vicious cycle of irregular learning and minimal advancement.

It is difficult to overestimate the meaning of a foreign language for modern society as it influences directly all the main life aspects in the development of every country. Nowadays, to be a highly qualified specialist signifies not only to be professional in your narrow sphere of knowledge but to master foreign languages as well. There exist different factors in providing successful foreign language teaching. One of the most important among them belongs to Psychology. Deep understanding of various psychological aspects may help teachers to solve many key moments in their work: to find a proper method of working in every students' group; to realize the right approach to students according to their skills and abilities taking into account complicated age peculiarities; to provide high motivation in foreign language mastering; to overcome natural problems, so called "barriers" appearing in the process of language studying.¹

Pedagogical psychology is closely connected with developmental and age psychology, which study age dynamics of person's mental development, ontogenesis of mental process and psychological quality of developing person. Ontogenesis refers to the sequence of events involved in the development of an individual organism from its birth to its death. This developmental history often involves a move from simplicity to higher complexity. So, all problems of development and age psychology are considered on the basis of accounting person's age features. Pedagogical and age psychology in their researching are based on the theories of General Psychology, which opens the general psychological laws, studies mental processes, mental conditions and person's individual and psychological peculiarities.

¹ THE ROLE OF PSYCHOLOGY IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES I. G. Chebotarova Kyiv, National Technical University of Ukraine

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